

ASSESSMENT OF ILLEGAL POACHING AND CONSERVATION STRATEGIES FOR THE CRITICALLY ENDANGERED INDIAN PANGOLIN (*MANIS CRASSICAUDATA*) IN POTOHAR REGION, PUNJAB, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

The use of reliable ecological information to support evidence-based management decisions for critically threatened species is often limited by data availability and local ecological knowledge (LCK) is increasingly regarded as a significant source of knowledge for conservation. The Indian Pangolin, *Manis Crassicaudata*, is considered endangered even though it plays a vital role in the food chain because it eats termites and other insects. This study in Pakistan aims to assess the critically endangered Indian pangolin's ecological role, population status, and illegal trade level using local community knowledge. We conducted a questionnaire-based survey research and collected the most recent data of Indian pangolin with 200 respondents across different locations of four districts (Jhelum, Chakwal, Rawalpindi, and Islamabad) between March 2020- April 2022 in the Potohar region of Punjab province, Pakistan. The survey aimed to determine whether LCK can provide innovative insights for pangolin conservation. The illegal trade of pangolins was reported across all four districts: Jhelum (73%, n=41), Chakwal (61.81%, n=55), Islamabad (>78.5%, n=42), and Rawalpindi (48.5%, n=62). As insectivorous animals, Indian pangolins serve as pest controllers and are beneficial for the ecosystem by protecting crops and forests. However, the illegal trade continues, with pangolin scales and other body parts, such as nails and flesh, being used by local communities and traded outside the country. Worldwide fund for nature plays an important role to stop the illegal trading of Indian Pangolin. This study stresses the need for detailed surveys to create conservation plans based on local community knowledge.

Index Term: Indian Pangolin, Jhelum, Chakwal, Rawalpindi, Islamabad, Local communities, Trade, Illegal, Ecological, Endangered.

INTRODUCTION

The Indian pangolin (*Manis crassicaudata*) represents a critical focal point in conservation efforts within Pakistan, where its endangered status is exacerbated by extensive illegal poaching and trade [1]. This species, renowned for its unique armoured scales and insectivorous diet, plays a crucial ecological role as a natural regulator of ant and termite populations, thereby contributing to ecosystem balance and health [2]. Despite its ecological significance, comprehensive biological data necessary for effective conservation strategies in Pakistan are notably lacking, reflecting the challenges inherent in studying elusive and vulnerable species [3]. The global demand for pangolin scales and other body parts, driven primarily by their use in traditional medicine across Asia, has led to a devastating surge in illegal hunting and trafficking [4]. Pakistan has emerged as a pivotal transit and consumption hub in this illicit trade network, further imperiling pangolin populations across its range [5]. The rampant exploitation of pangolins, compounded by habitat loss from agricultural expansion, urban development, and deforestation, underscores the urgent need for robust conservation measures [6].

Local Community Knowledge (LCK) has increasingly been recognized as a valuable source of information for understanding the behaviour, distribution, and threats faced by species like the Indian pangolin [1]. Communities residing near pangolin habitats possess intimate insights into local ecology and traditional practices that directly impact species survival [7]. By engaging local communities through participatory research approaches and structured surveys, conservationists can glean invaluable data to supplement scientific research and inform targeted conservation strategies. The Indian pangolin's ecological significance extends beyond its role as a pest controller [8]. By feeding on ants and termites, pangolins mitigate agricultural pest damage, thereby indirectly benefiting human livelihoods [9]. Their burrowing activities aerate soils and create microhabitats that support diverse flora and fauna, underscoring their importance in maintaining ecosystem integrity and resilience [7]. Understanding these ecological interactions is pivotal for designing conservation interventions that safeguard pangolins and their habitats.

Conservation efforts for the Indian pangolin in Pakistan face multifaceted challenges. The illegal wildlife trade remains a primary threat, driven by the high demand for pangolin scales in traditional medicine markets across Asia [10]. Despite international regulations under CITES (Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora), enforcement remains inadequate, allowing illegal trade networks to thrive [11]. Additionally, habitat fragmentation and degradation due to agricultural expansion and urbanization continue to diminish suitable pangolin habitats, exacerbating population declines [12].

This study aims to comprehensively address the conservation challenges faced by the critically endangered Indian *Manis crassicaudata* in Pakistan. It seeks to investigate the ecological role of pangolins as pest regulators in the Potohar region, quantify the extent and impact of illegal trade across selected districts (Jhelum, Chakwal, Rawalpindi, and Islamabad), explore local community knowledge to understand perceptions and

attitudes towards pangolin conservation and develop evidence-based conservation strategies and policy recommendations. By integrating scientific research with local community insights, the study aims to fill crucial knowledge gaps and contribute towards effective management and conservation of Indian pangolins, thereby ensuring their long-term survival in Pakistan.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The research was conducted in the four districts of Potohar region (Jhelum, Chakwal, Rawalpindi, and Islamabad) as seen in **Figure 1**. Historically significant, the area showcases remnants of the Soanian culture, evidenced by archaeological finds such as tools, artefacts, coins, and other relics (Gayen, Bhattacharya, Banerjee, Chatterjee, & Chaudhuri, 2024).

Fig 1: A. Map of district Chakwal, Rawalpindi, and Jhelum and B. Map of Margala Hills National Park

Data Collection

The study was a collaborative effort involving the World Wildlife Fund (WWF) Pakistan, Department of Wildlife Punjab, and Department of Forestry Punjab. Data collection relied on a structured questionnaire survey administered through interviews across seven distinct participant categories: labourers, farmers, hunters, students, teachers, forest guards, and wildlife watchers.

In **Figure 2(A)** explores the fresh burrow of a pangolin (KALLAR SYEDAN) **Figure 2(B)** shows stuck and cached **Figure 2(C)** explores an injured Indian pangolin at Marghazar Zoo Islamabad and **Figure 2(D)** shows rescued pangolin at Marghazar zoo. These categories were selected to encompass a diverse range of community perspectives on the Indian pangolin's ecological significance, the extent of illegal trade, and various aspects of its life cycle and interactions within the local ecosystem (Zanvo, 2022).

Fig 2: (A) Looking for a Fresh burrow of Pangolin (Kallar Syedan) (B) stuck and cached (C) injured Indian Pangolin at Marghazar Zoo Islamabad and (D) A rescued pangolin at Marghazar Zoo

Questionnaire Design and Implementation

Participants were selected from both rural villages and urban centres within the study area, ensuring a representative sample willing to engage in the research process. Interviews were conducted using a structured question-answer format tailored to gather insights into local attitudes, knowledge, and behaviours related to pangolin conservation and exploitation. Exclusion criteria were applied to ensure interviews were conducted only with individuals aged 18 years and above, respecting ethical guidelines and local regulations [13].

Data Authenticity and Geographic Verification

To verify the authenticity of participant responses and interview locations, the research employed MAP MARKER software. This tool ensured accurate geospatial referencing, crucial for validating reported data on pangolin sightings, habitat use, and hunting practices [14].

Statistical Data Analysis

Following the describe procedure, data analysis was done by using descriptive statistics to find patterns and trends within the gathered information by [15, 16]. We used statistical methods in SPSS software version 16.0 to investigate responses that differed throughout study areas by [17]. This analytical method allowed for a comprehensive exploration of local perceptions and behaviours towards pangolins, shedding light on key factors influencing their conservation status in the region.

Frequency and Percentage Calculation

Frequency (f) was calculated using the formula $= \frac{1}{n}$, where n represents the total number of samples. Percentages were derived as $\text{Percentage} = \frac{f}{n} * 100$, providing a quantitative basis to understand the prevalence of specific responses and behaviors related to pangolin conservation and exploitation [18].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Overview of Respondent Characteristics

The survey gathered comprehensive data from 200 respondents representing equal ratio in all districts various demographics including farmers, hunters, wildlife watchers, forest guards, teachers, students, and labourers. Predominantly, interviews were conducted with male participants residing in the study area throughout their lives [19].

General Information about Indian Pangolin

Respondents provided detailed insights into the general characteristics of the *Manis crassicaudata*. They recognized the pangolin as a mammal primarily through photographs, confirming its nocturnal (49.5%, $n=93$), diurnal (24.5%, $n=45$), or both behaviours (26.5%, $n=49$). The majority observed pangolins feeding on insects such as

ants and termites (79.5%, n=159), while a minority noted their occasional consumption of greenery (18.5%, n=37) and fruits (0.5%, n=1). Regarding reproduction, most respondents (87%, n=174) were unaware of the pangolin's reproductive rate. However, those with knowledge reported an average of 2 offspring per year (8.5%, n=17 for 2 offspring; 3.5%, n=7 for 1 offspring; 1%, n=2 for 3-5 offspring). A significant number (93.5%, n=187) claimed to have seen pangolins in their natural habitat, predominantly in forests (96.5%, n=181), with few sightings in confiscated conditions (3.2%, n=6) or decreased (0.5%, n=1)

Reported Sightings and Habitats

Respondents reported sightings of pangolins over the past decade, with 39.5% (n=79) witnessing one pangolin, and 33.5% (n=67) observing 2-3 pangolins. The frequency decreased with increased sightings, with 7.5% (n=15) reporting 3-5 sightings, and smaller percentages for 5-10 (4%, n=8), 10-20 (3.5%, n=7), and more than 20 sightings (1.5%, n=3). A small percentage (4.5%, n=9) reported not seeing any pangolins in the past decade (**Table 1A**). Respondents also provided details on the time since their last pangolin sighting, with 38.5% (n=77) reporting sightings more than a year ago, and 37% (n=74) reporting sightings more than five years ago (**Table 1B**). Moreover, respondents shared the frequency of pangolin sightings over their lifetime, with 27.5% (n=55) reporting two sightings, and substantial numbers reporting multiple sightings ranging from 4-5 times (27%, n=54) to more than 10 times (14.5%, n=29) (**Table 1C**). The results highlight widespread familiarity with the Indian pangolin among local communities, coupled with significant gaps in knowledge regarding its reproductive behaviour and ecological needs. The frequency of sightings indicates persistent presence in natural habitats, albeit with declining encounter rates over time. These findings underscore the importance of targeted conservation efforts to mitigate threats such as habitat loss and illegal trade, which continue to jeopardize pangolin populations in the region [20].

Table 1: Respondents' details about pangolins over the last 10 years, including the duration of sightings and the total number of sightings in their lifetime

Colum	No. of Pangolins	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
A. Pangolin Sightings Over the Last 10 Year	01	79	39.5
	2-3	67	33.5
	3-5	15	7.5
	5-10	8	4.0
	10-20	7	3.5
	More than 20	3	1.5
	No one	9	4.5
	Have not seen	12	6.0
	Total	200	100
B. Duration of Pangolin Sightings	Time Duration	Frequency(f)	Percent (%)
	1-7 days	7	3.5
	7-30days	4	2.0
	30-90days	10	5.0
	90-180days	4	2.0

	180-360days	12	6.0
	More than a year	77	38.5
	More than 5 years	74	37.0
	Total	188	94.0
	Missing data	12	6.0
	Total	200	100.0
C. Lifetime Pangolin Sightings	No. of Times	Frequency(f)	Percent (%)
	Once	31	15.5
	Twice	55	27.5
	4-5 times	54	27.0
	6-10 times	19	9.5
	More than 10 times	29	14.5
	Total	188	94.0
	Missing data	12	6.0
	Total	200	100.0

Misconceptions and Cultural Beliefs About Pangolins

There is a common misconception that pangolins live in graves, which is entirely false. Due to their burrowing behaviour, people mistakenly think they inhabit graves. Some also confuse pangolins with honey badgers that consume dead organisms. In our survey, respondents (n=147) reported that these misconceptions were incorrect, with only (n=12) affirming the misconceptions and (n=41) being unaware.

Specifically, (n=151) respondents stated that pangolins do not eat dead bodies, (n=3) claimed they do, and (n=46) were unsure. Notably, the (n=3) respondents who believed pangolins eat human remains admitted they had never witnessed this behaviour, disproving the myth. Cultural beliefs varied, with (n=98) respondents asserting that pangolin scales protect against evil spirits, (n=50) denying this belief, and (n=52) being uncertain.

Responses and Behaviours Towards Pangolins

When encountering pangolins, (n=103) respondents reported killing them with an axe, (n=21) used stones, (n=52) employed dogs, (n=18) used smoke or toxic gases, and (n=6) used other methods like hot rods or boiling as detail seen in **Figure 3**. Conversely, (n=115) respondents stated they now leave pangolins alive, a change attributed to wildlife conservation efforts.

Meanwhile, (n=26) still kill them on sight, (n=54) capture them, and (n=5) merely threaten them. Additionally, (n=188) respondents claimed they never killed a pangolin, while (n=12) admitted to capturing one. Of those, (n=3) killed one pangolin, (n=1) killed two, (n=1) killed 3-5, and (n=1) killed 10-20 in their lifetime. The remaining (n=6) released captured pangolins.

Fig 3: Response of people when they see pangolin

Reasons for Killing Pangolins

Respondents (n=126) reported that pangolins are not killed, while (n=68) cited illegal trade, (n=3) mentioned medicinal use, (n=2) noted self-defence, and (n=1) mentioned retaliatory killing in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Reasons for Killing Indian Pangolins According to the Local Community

Reasons for Killing	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
For illegal trade	68	34.0
For medicinal use	3	1.5
For self-defence	2	1.0
Retaliatory killing	1	0.5

Perceptions and Impacts of Pangolins

Respondents (n=108) stated they are not afraid of pangolins, while (n=70) admitted fear, and (n=22) were uncertain. Most farmers (n=137) believed pangolins do not destroy crops, (n=29) thought they did, and (n=34) were unsure. Reasons given for crop destruction included finding food (n=19), making burrows (n=1), both reasons (n=7), and uncertainty (n=2). When asked about the extent of crop damage, (n=27) respondents reported minimal damage, and (n=2) were unsure. Respondents also reported that pangolins damaged crops (n=16), destroyed soil (n=4), or were unsure (n=9). Additionally, (n=24) respondents had not seen pangolins destroy crops, while (n=5) had witnessed it.

Benefits of Pangolins

In terms of benefits, (n=37) respondents viewed pangolins as beneficial, (n=18) disagreed, and (n=145) were unsure. Among those who saw benefits, (n=31) noted pest control, and (n=5) mentioned soil aeration. Regarding confiscation, (n=169) respondents had not seen confiscated pangolins, whereas (n=31) had as mentioned in **Table 3**. Among respondents, (n=2) reported seeing people beating pangolins, (n=1) saw a pangolin eating, (n=13) witnessed sales, (n=11) saw people entertaining themselves with pangolins, and (n=3) reported other activities. Additionally, (n=114) respondents expressed liking pangolins, (n=8) disliked them, and (n=78) had no strong feelings.

Table 3: Locations and Frequency of Confiscated Pangolin Sightings

Location	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Salli\Jehlum	2	1.0
Padrali\Jehlum	1	0.5
Bangyal\Jehlum	1	0.5
Beth\Jehlum	1	0.5
Potha\Jehlum	1	0.5
Lari Shahnawaz\Chakwal	1	0.5
Amrila\Chakwal	1	0.5
Dill Jaba\Chakwal	1	0.5
Rawal Dam\ Islamabad	1	0.5
Rawalpindi	1	0.5
Margalla Hills\Isl	1	0.5
Mori Khatran\Isl	1	0.5
Tarnol\ Kohat	1	0.5
Sehr\Rawalpindi	2	1.0
Band\Rwp	4	2.0
Bharya Forest\Rwp	1	0.5
Narh\Rwp	1	0.5
Kahuta\Rwp	1	0.5
Mora Patha\Rwp	1	0.5
Chenam\Rwp	1	0.5
Bura Ayal\Rwp	1	0.5
Sangani\Rwp	1	0.5
Bhalakhar\Rwp	3	1.5
Total	30	15.0

Population Status and Threats Analysis

The status of the Indian pangolin population in the area is a critical concern. According to the respondents, (n=23) reported that the overall population is increasing, (n=92) noted that it is decreasing, (n=13) observed that it is stable, and (n=72) were unsure about the overall population status. The primary reasons cited for the decline include illegal trade, with (n=52) respondents attributing the decrease to this factor, followed by illegal hunting, which (n=36) respondents identified as a significant threat. Additionally, (n=4) respondents indicated that climate change is contributing to the population decline of Indian pangolins.

In terms of historical population trends, (n=135) respondents believed that there were many pangolins in the past, indicating a significant presence previously. Conversely, (n=10) respondents reported that there were fewer pangolins in the past, and (n=4) felt the population was neither high nor low historically. A notable portion, (n=51) of respondents, were uncertain about the historical population status. These responses reflect a general perception of decline, corroborated by the identified threats of illegal trade, hunting, and climate change. This analysis underscores the urgent need for conservation efforts to address these threats and stabilize the pangolin population in the area as seen in **Figure 4**.

Fig 4: The ratio of overall population status of pangolins in a particular area

Illegal trade Analysis

A wide variety of responses were received from local respondents regarding the hunting and killing of pangolins. Of the respondents, (n=127) stated that there is hunting/killing of pangolins, while (n=73) reported that there is no hunting in the area. Cultural beliefs play a significant role in the reasons behind pangolin killings. Some people consider pangolins lucky, while others use them in traditional medicines. Consequently, (n=68) respondents indicated that the killing is for illegal trade, (n=8) for medicinal use, (n=2) for self-defence, and (n=1) as retaliatory killing. When asked about the specific uses of pangolins, (n=79) respondents stated that the whole pangolin is used, and (n=38) reported that only their scales are used for illegal trade. Respondents also described the methods of illegal smuggling of Indian pangolins: (n=95) mentioned that smugglers have contact with local dealers, (n=23) said they trade through online selling, and (n=9) reported using both methods. Respondents also provided information on the cost of Indian pangolins. (n=36) said the cost is around 10k-20k, (n=51) responded that it is 30k-40k, (n=22) reported 40k-

50k or above, (n=7) mentioned the cost depends on weight/kg and size, and (n=11) did not know the cost. Regarding the level of hunting in their village, (n=132) respondents stated that it has decreased, (n=12) reported an increase, and (n=56) were unsure. When asked about the locations where pangolins are smuggled, (n=7) respondents mentioned all of Pakistan, (n=3) specified Islamabad, (n=1) stated Rawalpindi, and (n=1) indicated across the border, while (n=183) did not know the exact location. Additionally, (n=144) respondents reported that the primary trade is outside of the country, (n=11) stated it is inside the country, and (n=45) were unsure. Different groups of people involved in pangolin killings were identified: (n=106) reported nomads, (n=52) local hunters, (n=38) farmers, and (n=4) mentioned outside hunters.

Sentiment Analysis of Pangolin Role in Ecosystem

Pangolins play a crucial role in our ecosystem by feeding on insects, especially ants and termites, making them natural pest controllers that help protect plants and crops. Despite this vital role, awareness about pangolins and their conservation is lacking in many communities. According to a survey conducted among respondents (n=98), there were varied responses regarding the role of pangolins in the ecosystem. A majority (n=72) recognized their positive role, citing insect control as the primary benefit. Some respondents (n=2) also mentioned their contribution to soil health, while others (n=6) highlighted their potential medicinal value and (n=13) appreciated their natural beauty. However, a small number of respondents (n=5) expressed negative views, considering pangolins harmful to humans, plants, and soil. Despite these contrasting opinions, there is a general lack of awareness (n=97) about pangolins among the public as seen in

Figure 5.

Fig 5: Sentiment Analysis of Pangolin Role in Ecosystem

The World Wildlife Fund (WWF) is actively involved in pangolin conservation efforts. Through research programs and awareness campaigns, WWF aims to protect and conserve wildlife, including pangolins. Respondents (n=113) acknowledged the positive impact of WWF's activities, while some (n=3) expressed negative views, and many (n=84) were unaware of their efforts. WWF's awareness campaigns, conducted through various media, have had mixed responses from the public. Before the campaigns, some respondents (n=20) neither liked nor disliked pangolins, but after the campaigns, more respondents (n=108) expressed a liking for them.

However, there were still some (n=40) who expressed dislike or remained neutral. When asked about personal views on pangolin conservation, most respondents (n=190) expressed a desire to conserve them, citing reasons such as their role in protecting plants, their benefits to humans, their beauty, and their non-harmful nature.

In terms of conservation strategies, respondents suggested various approaches, including raising awareness (n=104), stopping illegal trade and killing (n=33), cooperating with wildlife departments (n=50), and implementing stricter rules and laws (n=13). Government departments and NGOs are actively working to conserve pangolins.

Respondents identified the wildlife department (n=120) as the primary agency involved, followed by the Islamabad Wildlife Management Board (IWMB) (n=13), the Department of Forestry (n=7), and a combination of wildlife and forestry departments (n=7). However, some respondents (n=53) felt that no significant efforts were being made in their area.

Overall, there is a sense of satisfaction (n=151) among respondents regarding the progress of conservation efforts, with many acknowledging the efforts of these departments in spreading awareness (n=55), enforcing laws (n=57), and implementing various measures (n=23). However, there is also a significant portion (n=49) of respondents who are not satisfied, suggesting that more efforts should be made, particularly in terms of awareness campaigns (n=31) and stricter enforcement (n=18).

Local communities can also play a crucial role in pangolin conservation by refraining from killing or trading pangolins (n=105), cooperating with wildlife departments (n=12), protecting pangolins (n=27), and spreading awareness (n=15). Illegal hunting and killing of pangolins remain a concern in some districts.

According to the survey, respondents reported illegal hunting in Jhelum (73%), Chakwal (61.81%), Islamabad (78.5%), and Rawalpindi (48.5%) as seen in **Figure 6**. These findings highlight the need for continued conservation efforts and stricter enforcement of laws to protect pangolins from extinction.

Fig 6: District-wise comparison of hunting of Indian pangolin

DISCUSSION

In Pakistan this species is classified as endangered (Mahmood et al., 2019). Under Punjab Wildlife Acts and Rules (1974) it is included in Phase Three of the Third category and is therefore protected throughout the time [21]. However, these animals are hunted for commercial purposes [22], although there is limited data about the pangolin's trade or their life threats [23]. Data for hunting and trade is needed to design effective animal conservation strategies. Without conservation efforts, the population of Indian pangolin could continue to decline and could be lost in Pakistan.

Basic information about biology and ecology, including habitat/preferences, population, and eating habits, is also needed for conservational efforts. It is found that this species is widespread in all four Plateau regions and occupies 18% more of the Plateau than previously recorded [24]. It is possible that this species expanded its range due to hunting pressure or, which may have previously been neglected in some areas due to its hidden nature.

Given the low fertility rate of species [25], it can be removed from the Plateau without improved protection strategies. Although poachers do not kill male Indian pangolins but 16 out of 21 pangolins recorded in the study were male [25]. Although this raises the proportion of male sex bias, the sample size is very small, and males may be more mobile, more active or easier to capture.

Although pangolins are sold internationally in Asia [25], CITES does not record these trades in one place. Data from the Indian pangolin (including origin, species, and number of traders) during July 2000 (when trade caught in the four Asian pangolin species became active) and in studies in 2013 indicate commercial status and provided the most comprehensive methods for analysing illegal trade [26]. Historically, Asian pangolin species have been used locally for food (e. g as a source of protein, healthy foods, and as an ingredient in traditional medicine), popular in China, but also international trade with its scales [25]. Capture data and trading records show that between July 2000 and December 2013 there were at least 886 arrests involving Indian pangolins, an estimated 227,278 illegal traffickers [27]. Trade was the average (41%) for living and dead (31%) and meat (26%) [28].

There are no reports of pangolin use in Pakistan, and limited local trade in pangolin scales does not account for the large number of pangolins killed. Therefore, it is concluded that the high level of poaching is driven by the need for international trade. Currently, the Indian pangolin's penalty fine is PKR 10,000 and/or 1 week in jail. This is an ineffective barrier, as one adult pangolin can be sold for PKR 50,000 (c. USD 500). Recent reports indicate that species have declined by 79% [29] and that the decline continues. To reduce the poaching of Indian pangolin and to protect the people of the Potohar Plateau it is recommended that additional efforts, to monitor and ensure and increase the penalties for poaching. The data received our findings from local authorities at the district level (Department of Wildlife and Parks, Punjab Government) and have intensified their efforts to protect the pangolin in the study area. There are now a few reports of pangolin shootings. However, this may also indicate that Indian pangolins continue to decline on the Potohar Plateau and that hunters are finding fewer individuals.

This study provides the first wide-angle conservation research-based investigation to use LCK for the estimation of the Indian pangolin's population status and the scale of its illegal trade in the Potohar region. This research work also allows large-scale data to gather previous and present pangolin population abundance and threats as well as the local community's beliefs about pangolin. The data is necessary for the development of essential conservation management strategies. Moreover, this survey elaborates on the probable constant survival of pangolins in all studied areas. Before this survey, society's concern had been raised that May Indian pangolins have already been pushed to extinction; no recent basic data were available to deeply evaluate the possibility. This data obtained from the survey also delivers an important perception of effective upcoming conservation strategies for pangolins.

Open and closed questions about specific characteristics of pangolins effectively understand information on the patterns of exploitation by supporting past studies which have indicated that LCK surveys can produce effective results on conservational strategies and ways of illegal trade activities. The results of this study assist the current IUCN status of Indian pangolin as critically endangered. However, pangolins still exist in several areas of Potohar region, and the survival of populations appears threatened by

continued illegal trade, poaching, and use of meat and their scales. There is a dire need to transform methods for monitoring and assessing Indian pangolin's status as well as threats at a large scale. These results also suggest that wide-scale LCK surveys can contribute to this noble goal because these can be inexpensive as well as rapidly conducted over large geographic areas as compared to other methods to detect pangolins related to all information. There is a still need on an urgent basis to transform and strengthen conservation management goals for pangolins, contributing to the survival and promotion of conservation of these amazing animals in Potohar region remains possible and could set a chief example on a global scale.

CONCLUSION

Indian pangolins are reported as an endangered species in Pakistan. Local community knowledge (LCK) surveys are inexpensive and relatively rapid to conduct over large geographic areas in comparison to the other methods to collect data about pangolins. These surveys can be useful in collection of the data about pangolin population trends, sightings, and patterns of exploitation with the passage of time rather than only providing, an estimation of the current situation. As compared to 4 districts (Jhelum, Chakwal, Rawalpindi, and Islamabad) this study concluded that district Islamabad is a major hub for illegal trade as 78.5% of pangolins are being traded in this region. In Rawalpindi, there were more sightings of pangolins noticed during the last 10 years (n=57, 50%) and fewer sightings were noticed in Jhelum (n=41, 30%) respectively. It is also concluded that the Indian pangolin plays an important role in the ecosystem by protecting crops and forests from pests (n=103, 95%). There is a dire need to transform strategies for the assessment and monitoring of threats and the Indian pangolin's status on a wide scale. This study suggests that wide-angle LCK surveys can play an important part in achieving this goal. Therefore, by controlling poverty and using awareness programs we can conserve the whole wildlife as well as Indian pangolin.

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